

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH AGE.

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Аннотация: В этой статье мы можем узнать возрастные психологические особенности дошкольников и их значение для здорового развития ребенка.

Ключевое слово: ребенок, самостоятельная деятельность, дошкольники, психология, здоровье

Annotation: in this article we can find out the psychological characteristics of preschool children regarding age and their importance in the healthy development of the child.

Keyword: child, independent activity, preschool children, psychology, healthy

After a child turns three years old and goes into preschool age, his physical growth slows down somewhat. The unevenness in the physical growth of the child continues even during this period. For example, we can see the growth of the height before the age of one year from the birth of a child in the table below. Indicators of physical development in preschool age: age 0-1 1-2 2-3 3-4 4-5 5-6 6-7 height (cm) 25 40 8 4 6-7 7-8 10 the body of a preschool child, in particular, due to the lengthening of the legs, changes in the overall proportion in the body of preschool age from 3 to 7 years Basically, it is from this period that the child's independent activities develop and personal individual characteristics (personal qualities) begin to find content. From Russian educators P.F.Lesgaft believes that the pre-school age of a person is such a period during which it is determined what character traits will appear in the future, and the basis of their moral qualities will arise. P. on the importance of the preschool age period in human maturation.F.This opinion of Lesgaft was expressed by the Russian pedagogue A.S.It fully corresponds to the following opinion of Makarenko. A.S.Makarenko spoke about the need to raise children from a very small period, and the most important foundations of upbringing are laid during the period of the child's up to five years. It was during this period that the entire upbringing made up 90% of the upbringing process. Indeed, the period of the child in preschool age is such a content and active period that this period will definitely leave its reflection in

the future growth of the child. Therefore, the preschool age period is extremely responsible in terms of the power of influence.

When a child moves from the first to the preschool period, serious changes occur in his entire living conditions. First, when a child reaches kindergarten age, his range of activity is greatly expanded, and his independence is further increased. His games, his behavior also begin to have a different meaning. Secondly, the role of speech in the entire activity of the child goes beyond. Thirdly, after the child reaches preschool age, he begins to be brought up by a special educator on the basis of a specific program. These changes that occur in the living conditions of a preschool child do not affect his physical and psychically growing maturity. The physical development of a preschool child, as we have already said, corresponds to the fact that the period of the child's fastest physical growth is one to two years of age.

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Indicators of physical development in preschool age:	age 0-1	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7
height (cm)	25	40	84	6-7	7-8	10	

the body of a preschool child, in particular, due to the lengthening of his legs, changes in the overall proportion in his torso. In the preschool age period, the child's legs grow relatively more. However, even so, the bones of a child under 6-7 years old are not yet well hardened, that is, in a grayish state. Preschool children are very mobile, despite the fact that their legs and muscles are not yet energetic. After the child reaches the age of 7, a certain degree of Flexion occurs in the neck of the spine to the forward side and in the chest to the back. Later, the child's spine is preserved in this form. It is of great importance that the vertebral bone is preserved in such a way that the child is correct in Kaddi-Basti. The skull of a kindergarten-age child also grows rapidly. After the child is three years old, the back and upper sides of the skull bone grow rapidly. In preschool age, serious changes also occur in the internal organs of the child. For example, in terms of volume, the child's heart is 4-5 times larger than the baby's heart, but his muscles will not yet be sufficiently strengthened. That is why the heart of a child of kindergarten age cannot squeeze enough blood for the body in one contraction. This is also the reason why the child's heart beats relatively quickly than the heart of older people. Chunonchi, if the heart of a 1-year-old child squeezes 10.2 cubic/cm of blood in one contraction, the heart of a 7-year-old child squeezes 23 cubic/cm of blood in one contraction. The heart of

an adult, on the other hand, squeezes more than 60 cubic/ cm of blood in one contraction. Due to the relatively faster functioning of the heart in the preschool age period, the child's blood pressure becomes slightly stronger than in older people.

The growth of the nervous system of preschool children in the development of the psyche of preschool children plays a huge role in the changes that occur in their nervous systems. The most strongly progressive period of the nervous systems of children falls on the period up to the age of 1 year. The average weight of the newborn's cranium comes from 380-400 g. Until the child reaches kindergarten age, his brain develops and almost triples. Thus, children of kindergarten age reach a brain weight of 1100-1200 g. During the further improvement of the nervous system in preschool children, nerve fibers that connect the Centers of the cranial cortex with each other also begin to be covered with myelin sheaths. The coating of nerve fibers in the brain with the myelin sheath is of great importance for the process of reflection, that is, for psychic processes and their development. When nerve fibers myelinate, firstly, the rapid passage of excitations through nerve fibers is ensured, and secondly, it ensures that excitation only goes to the corresponding Center. This results in relatively rapid formation of conditioned reflexes (temporary connections) caused by the action of various triggers acting on the body from the external environment. In addition, a clear course of each excitation to the appropriate center ensures that children of kindergarten age can handle their actions with dexterity.

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